

Understanding Stereocilia Mechanics in the Cochlear Partition with a Finite-Element Model

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Abstract. The basal cochlear partition in human differs from that of typical laboratory mammals. In the basal region of the human cochlea, the osseous spiral lamina (OSL) exhibits a radial width approximately ten times greater than that of the basilar membrane (BM). In the *classic view* of the cochlear partition, the inner pillar cell (PC) is next to the OSL which serves as a rotational pivot point for the organ of Corti (OoC). The human cochlear partition has a soft tissue bridge that connects the OSL and the BM proper. Consequently, the foot of the inner PC sits in a different relative position within the human cochlear partition, separated from the OSL. This produces a possible rotational and translation motion of the PCs and OoC. The resulting difference in motion has been hypothesized to produce a difference in hair bundle motion, and therefore transduction. We examine this structure-function relationship of the OSL and OoC with a finite-element box model of the human cochlea. Geometrical features of the model include an OSL with two bony layers with a soft inner layer, orthotropic BM, an input velocity at the oval window, and a round window membrane. Calibration of the model consisted of comparing model outputs with experimental data, including the frequency-place map, radial profile motion measurements, and frequency response measurements made in fresh human cochleae using OCT vibrometry. With this model, we aim to address questions about the OSL and OoC and how it relates to function in the human cochlea. For example, how does the OSL, being further from the inner pillar cells, influence motion of the reticular lamina and the BM?

INTRODUCTION

The “*classic view*” of the cochlear partition comprises several characteristics. (1) The osseous spiral lamina (OSL) is generally much less mobile compared to the soft tissues of the partition. (2) The pillar cells (PCs) and tunnel of Corti (ToC) are positioned at the lateral edge of the OSL and thus the OoC pivots around the foot of the inner PC (3) The basilar membrane (BM) is primarily displaced in the transverse direction by the traveling wave and the pressure difference between the scalae. (4) The transverse motion in a radial cross section of the cochlear partition reaches a peak near the outer hair cells (OHCs) and outer PC. These combined characteristics result in transduction where an upward deflection of the BM causes excitatory motion of the hair cell stereocilia, i.e., deflection of the stereocilia towards the lateral direction.

The human basal cochlea differs from the *classic view*. There is a bridge region between the OSL and the BM proper made of soft tissue. The presence of a bridge region is such that the foot of the inner PCs does not sit at the lateral tip of the OSL as in the *classic view*, but instead the foot of the inner PC is situated apart from the OSL on top of the highly mobile soft tissue of the BM-bridge. Additionally, in contrast to the *classic view*, the limbus is not entirely adjacent to the OSL bone, but rather also adjacent to part of the bridge region. Thus, the limbal attachment of the TM can move with the mobile bridge.

In human, the motion of the cochlear partition as a function of radial position has been shown to be around the inner PCs and ToC instead of at the location of the OHC and outer PC in the *classic view* [1]. As a result, it was hypothesized that (1) an upward BM deflection would cause the limbal attachment of the TM to be mobile and (2) the pivoting of the PCs might be different due to the presence of the bridge. The net result is that stereocilia motion could

deflect in the inhibitory direction during upward BM motion rather than in the excitatory motion as in the *classic view*. This hypothesis has yet to be tested experimentally.

The goal of the present study was to examine the stereocilia motion in the human cochlea with a finite element model of the cochlear partition. First, a full-length box model was developed and tuned using optical coherence tomography (OCT) vibrometry measurements [2]. A more detailed shortened version of the model was then developed to facilitate the calculation of the stereocilia motion between the RL and TM.

METHODS

The model is a tapered box model with two fluid ducts (scala vestibuli/media and scala tympani) and the cochlear partition in between. Firstly, a 32-mm full-length cochlear model (Fig. 1A and 1B) was developed and calibrated to OCT measurements obtained in a cadaveric human temporal bone through the round window membrane from the basal 12-13 kHz region with a healthy-looking organ of Corti (OoC) [2]. Model geometrical parameters were taken from measurements of histological sections of human cochleae. The novelty of the model was that it incorporated specific anatomical details of the human cochlear partition, in particular a mobile OSL and a bridge region separating the inner PC from the OSL. In addition, the OSL was modeled with two bony layers with a softer middle layer. Material properties were either taken from literature or tuned to produce responses similar to the OCT measurements [2] and within ± 1 mm place compared to the half-octave shifted (i.e., representing a passive cochlea) Greenwood map [3]. The model material properties are summarized in Table 1. The full-length model did not include the stereocilia for the OHCs due to computational limits.

TABLE 1. Model parameter values. The basilar membrane is orthotropic (L = longitudinal, R = radial, T = transverse) whereas all other structures are isotropic.

Structure	Young's modulus (MPa)	Shear modulus (MPa)	Poisson's ratio	Density (kg/m ³)	Damping
OSL bone	10,000	-	0.3	2,000	0.1
OSL inner layer	3,000	-	0.485	1,100	0.1
Basilar membrane/bridge	0.1(L), 100(R), 0.1(T)	0.03(LR), 33.3(RT), 0.03(LT)	0.485	1,100	0.1
Limbus	10	-	0.485	1,100	0.1
Organ of Corti	10	-	0.485	1,100	0.1
Pillar cells	100	-	0.485	1,100	0.1
Tectorial membrane	0.03	-	0.485	1,100	0.1
Stereocilia	1,000	-	0.485	1,100	0.1
Round window membrane	1.4	-	0.485	1,100	0.8

The model was modified to be a “basal” version of the original full-length cochlear box model in order to accommodate more detailed structures related to transduction, i.e., the TM, stereocilia, and an OoC that distinguished PCs, ToC, and a soft tissue region encompassing the remainder of the OoC structures. The length of the basal model was 10 mm. The corresponding frequencies that have a best-frequency place in the basal model are 3-14 kHz [3]. For computational efficiency, stereocilia geometry was simplified in the model as one stereocilium every one mm (nine stereocilia in total). The basal model is shown in Figs. 1C and 1D.

The basal model mesh contained a mixture of tetrahedral, pyramidal, prism, and hexahedral elements, with 277,081 elements in total and 1,850,873 degrees of freedom.

FIGURE 1. Model geometry. (A) Full-length human cochlear model. (B) Partition geometry at the base of the full-length model at the region of the dashed outline in A. (C) Basal human cochlear model. (D) Partition geometry at the base of the basal model at the region of the dashed outline in C. OoC = organ of Corti, PCs = pillar cells, TM = tectorial membrane, ToC = tunnel of Corti.

FIGURE 2. Schematic of the assessment of stereocilium (sc) angle θ_{sc} relative to reticular lamina (RL) angle θ_{RL} , where θ_{RL} is the angle of the RL relative to its horizontal rest angle. The difference between θ_{sc} and θ_{RL} is used to determine excitatory vs. inhibitory deflection, where a positive $\theta_{sc}-\theta_{RL}$ is excitatory, and negative is inhibitory. Counter-clockwise rotation denotes a positive angle (as seen in illustration) and clockwise rotation denotes a negative angle.

In order to assess the stereocilium deflection in the excitatory vs. inhibitory orientations relative to when the BM was maximally displaced towards the scala vestibuli, the angle of a stereocilium θ_{sc} was calculated relative to the angle of the reticular lamina (RL) θ_{RL} as shown in Fig. 2. Because the OoC moved approximately as a rigid body, the angle of the RL was approximated as the angle of the BM as it pivoted around its pinned lateral edge (at the spiral ligament). The stereocilium angle was calculated with respect to its vertical rest angle. A stereocilium angle that is greater than the RL angle represents excitatory deflection (tip towards the lateral side) and a smaller stereocilia angle with respect to the RL represents inhibitory deflection (tip towards to the medial side).

RESULTS

Basal model stereocilia motion relative to RL motion at all nine stereocilium locations along the length of the cochlea and at each of the six tested frequencies (200 Hz, 1 kHz, 3.15 kHz, 5 kHz, 8 kHz, and 11 kHz) is shown in Fig. 3. The point of interest in the motion cycle was that which corresponds to maximal BM deflection towards the scala vestibuli. The results are presented as binary, either excitatory or inhibitory, for each frequency-place combination. The majority of frequency-place combinations show inhibitory motion of the stereocilia, where the stereocilium is oriented so that it points medially with respect to the RL motion angle, corresponding to a direction of deflection consistent with the inhibitory direction for hair bundle transduction. Only four frequency-place combinations show excitatory stereocilia motion. These all occur at high frequencies and basally in the model, though not in a discernably predictable pattern. The majority result of inhibitory motion is inconsistent with the *classical view*, which postulates the opposite: that stereocilia are in the excitatory position at maximum deflection of the BM towards the scala vestibuli.

FIGURE 3. Stereocilia deflection relative to RL motion at the point of maximal BM deflection towards the scala vestibuli. Results are presented as binary, either excitatory (“Exc”, blue) or inhibitory (“Inh”, red), at the six frequencies tested and the nine stereocilium locations along the length of the model.

Two examples of snapshots of model motion at maximal BM deflection towards the scala vestibuli are shown in Fig. 4. Generally, the entire partition was mobile, including the OSL. Figure 4 left depicts an example of inhibitory motion of the stereocilium at 3 mm from the base and at 200 Hz, and figure 4 right depicts an example of excitatory motion of the stereocilium at 1 mm from the base. Although model motion results are exaggerated, the stereocilia motions are small and difficult to visually inspect outside of the calculation results presented in Fig. 3.

FIGURE 4. Example model inhibitory (left; location: 3 mm from the base, frequency: 200 Hz) and excitatory (right; location: 1 mm from the base, frequency: 8 kHz) motion results as a cross-section of the model geometry at maximum deflection towards the scala vestibuli.

DISCUSSION

Model results indicate that the stereocilia motion is predominantly opposite in the human model versus the *classic view*, a possibility suggested by Raufer et al. [1] based on a visual assessment rather than a simple physical model. How do we interpret the importance of this model result?

On the one hand, the model results provide a physical indication that stereocilia motion is different in humans. The model incorporates complexities of the human anatomy such as the bridge region separating the OoC and the OSL, a long mobile OSL, and a limbal attachment of the TM that is radially in line with the bridge region. Though it should be noted that while we are focused on human in this study, the presence of a bridge is not unique to human. The human cochlea has a bridge region along the entire length, but there are other examples, such as guinea pig and cat, that also have a bridge-like anatomy in the apical region [1].

On the other hand, a fundamentally opposite stereocilia deflection in humans would seem to be an improbable evolutionary feature. Such an unexpected result may indicate that our understanding of the key elements in cochlear models is inadequate. It requires a close examination of model details that may be oversimplified or omitted.

The material properties of the structures in the full-length box model were chosen from tuning the model to closely match human OCT measurements. However, added structures in the basal model (the TM, stereocilia, and PCs) may require additional parameter tuning.

The motion snapshots in Fig. 4 show that the cochlear partition has a different pivot point of the OoC than is seen in the *classic view*. This difference in pivot point holds for all frequencies and all locations and is likely a major factor influencing the opposite phase of the stereocilium deflection. How the OoC and thus the stereocilia deflection changes due to changes in TM, limbus and OoC Young's modulus needs to be further explored.

In conclusion, our simplified finite-element model is consistent with the interpretation suggested by Raufer et al. [1] that upward BM motion deflects OHC stereocilia in the inhibitory direction, opposite to the *classic view*.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[*Online Forum*]

Stephen Neely: In the first sentence of the Introduction, please consider replacing the phrase “is comprised of” with “comprises.”

Stephen Neely: When the PDF was printed, the greek letter theta appeared in the Fig. 2 caption but was missing in the last paragraph of the Methods section. Please check that all fonts used in the document are embedded in the PDF file.

[*Moderated Discussions*]

Dáibhid Ó Maoiléidigh: I was just wondering how do you assess or how do you know what the resting angle of the stereocilia are relative to the reticular lamina? It seems to me you are assuming the resting angle is positive, but if you have hair bundles that are not attached to the tectorial membrane, we know the resting angle is negative.

Andrew Tubelli: Yeah, so in this model, it's quite overly simplified perhaps, we're assuming a horizontal and a vertical axis, so the BM and RL are horizontal, the stereocilia in this model are vertical, so our resting position is vertical.

Jonathan Siegel: Yeah, I'm just trying to understand what this means. We have smaller animals with cochlear amplifiers that work perfectly well at even higher frequencies than humans, and maybe there's a difference in auditory nerve coding, but probably not above 16 kHz or so. Phase shouldn't matter there. What's the problem that the human cochlea has solved that isn't there in other animals? Do you have any sense of that? Why is this happening?

Andrew Tubelli: Why, I don't know. The answer is “I don't know,” but we are investigating the human cochlea because it does have these anatomical differences. Whether or not they translate to something that is better, or not, from other species, we can't really say. But, it's an interesting question.

Anthony Gummer: In your stick model of the organ of Corti, you didn't include the tectorial membrane. There's a very nice paper from Peter Dallos on the kinematics of the organ of Corti where he shows quite clearly that you have to include a lever in the tectorial membrane, and the motion of the stereocilia is a sort of net motion of the two, or relative motion of the two, the reticular lamina and the tectorial membrane. You should also have a lever under the tectorial membrane, because it's the relative motion of the tectorial membrane and the reticular lamina that is producing the motion of the stereocilia. Therefore, I was just wondering whether you might then... if you do the kinematics properly, whether you would get an excitatory motion in the classical sense.

Andrew Tubelli: Well, the green is the tectorial membrane, and so it does move along with the rest of the structures here. I suppose it is overly simplified and there are ways to add more, but thank you.